

THE IMPORTANCE OF FURNITURE IN THE INTERIOR OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Tashmatova Khosiyat Sidikovna
Zalotdinova Lolita Ramilevna

Lectures of the Department "Architektura" SamSACU

Abstract: The article outlines the principles of designing preschool institutions based on architects and numerous studies: projects that perform the function of a "huge space for games" with an open plan for children, and it is proposed to create favorable corners for children. The basic principles of creating an environment that motivates children to read and develops their mental, creative and physical abilities were determined. Preschool buildings are considered as a means of perceiving the world and social adaptation of children. A piece of furniture is attached to them as an example or material.

Keywords: preschool furniture, furniture for kindergartens, equipment for child care, furniture for preschoolers.

Components: Tables, Chairs, Toy Cabinets, Bookmaker Shelf, Easel, Blackboard, Wooden

Introduction. The principles of designing preschool institutions based on the research of psychologists, today architects around the world are also concerned about the question of what a modern preschool institution should be. At the end of the XX century, research in the field of child psychology was actively conducted, and all of them were somehow reflected in the modern architecture of kindergartens.

Design principles based on the research of psychologists According to Judith Seaver's study "Philosophy of Educational Approach", interior design should be directly related to the educational program, which includes structured classes (scheduled classes) and unstructured classes (allowing the child to choose classes) [1].

Pic. 1

With this in mind, the main trend in the design of modern preschool institutions should be the layout of

the premises of an "open structure" and the rejection of the traditional corridor system. In large rooms, areas for both relaxing and active games are created using movable partitions, different floor levels, various floor coverings and other methods. Children, following their inner impulses, choose for themselves what they want to do. Thus, a flowing space is formed without "free" places (Pic. 2) [3].

Pic. 2

Pic. 3

In 1994, another research experiment was conducted: another smaller "classroom" was created inside the standard classroom in the form of a box structure.

Being in a smaller room, children spent much more time on a certain activity than in a standard classroom [1]. It was concluded that the architects should provide more private, reduced spaces for children in the structure of the building. One example of such a design solution for a kindergarten with an open plan and private spaces is a kindergarten in Troms in Norway (Pic. 2) [4].

Psychologists have come to another conclusion that architects should take into account the visual horizons

of the child: windows at eye level of the child, horizontal elements corresponding to the height of the door (Pic. 3) [1, 5].

Thus, based on the above-mentioned studies, it was concluded that the environment that the architect creates for children should be nurtured and developed. Creating a comfortable environment for preschool children, the architect must follow the principles of:

- Open-plan premises;
- Providing the possibility of active movement in each room;
- Giving children the opportunity to explore, develop sensory experience (using various textured surfaces).
- Creating private spaces for relaxation, quiet games and private lessons;
- providing visual diversity of forms and spaces, creating contrasts;
- Communication with the external environment, the natural environment;
- Creating the mood of the space with the help of architecture, in accordance with its function. An example of the use of all of the above principles is the kindergarten Kids Troplo in Hamburg (Germany), designed by the architectural firm Kadawittfeldarchitektur [10].

Pic.4

Pic. 5

The facade of the building attracts attention with its interesting geometry, contrasting colors, bright color accents on a neutral background. The central two-level space is a huge place for outdoor games with a wide range of amenities for the child, allowing them to move and create. At the same time, the architects have taken care of secluded places where tired children can relax, read or draw. The main staircase (Pic. 4), in the central space, in addition to its original function, is an area for active games, movement, and can also serve as

a forum. Panoramic windows provide good lighting and visual interconnection of the interior space with the surrounding nature. Moreover, the kindergarten building is not only functional and flexible for future changes, but also energy efficient natural environment (Pic. 4).

Moreover, the kindergarten building is not only functional and flexible for future changes, but also energy efficient (Pic. 4). Basic principles of designing preschool institutions (using the example of the kindergarten Kids Troplo in Hamburg (Germany)). Conclusions Recently, architects in Russia have also begun to look for new and different design approaches to the organization of children's educational institutions. Studies were conducted on the influence of social needs and the psychology of children's perception on the architecture of the building and the organization of the interior space. Basically, these studies are aimed at finding new principles for designing school buildings [11, 12]. As for preschool institutions, this issue is less studied. This study can give a good start for a new step in the development of modern kindergartens in Uzbekistan.

Literature

1. Architectureofearlychildhood.com
2. M. Dudek, Kindergarten Architecture: A Space for Imagination (Rutledge, USA, 2013)
3. M. Galindo, Kindergartens: Educational Spaces (Brown, 2011)
4. archdaily.com/category/kindergarten
5. Children's Spaces: Architecture for Children (Australia, 2004)
6. Rakhmanova, M. B. (2024). FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION OF INNOVATIVE ARCHITECTURE OF MUSEUMS OF THE WORLD. Innovative: International Multidisciplinary Journal of Applied Technology (2995-486X), 308-312.
7. Keldiyor, K., va Xosiyat, T. (2024). Turar-joy binolarini loyihalashning xususiyatlari. Barqaror fuqarolik qurilishini boshqarish va muhandislik jurnali , 1 (2), 7. <https://doi.org/10.47134/scbmej.v1i2.2352>
9. Sidiqovna, T.K. (2023). Shahar va qishloq joylarda maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarini loyihalash usullari. Nexus: muhandislik fanining ilg'or tadqiqotlari jurnali , 2 (6), 56–59. <https://innosci.org/JISES/article/view/1456>

